

A Pilot Study on Evaluation of Formulated Herbal Hair Oil

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ABSTRACT

Hair follicles are surrounded by the dermis, but the cells are part of the epidermis and are separated from the dermis by the basallamina layer. The main aim of the study is to design and evaluation of versatile Herbal Hair Oil to prevent and control hair-related problems. The main objectives of the study are Provides hair conditioning, Prevention & control of hair fall, Reduce scalp irritation, Prevents premature greying of hair, Treats Dandruff, Relieves all types of headaches especially migraine & Hangover headaches gives a shiny and glossy appearance.

KEYWORDS: Hair, Dandruff, hair conditioning, hair fall

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INTRODUCTION

Hair is part of the integumentary system. Strands of hair originate from the base of living epithelial cells into the dermis which is called the hair follicle¹. Hair follicles are surrounded by the dermis, but the cells are part of the epidermis and are separated from the dermis by the basal lamina layer. Hair on the head protects it from the sun and heat loss². The duration of phases changes based on the location of hair, hormonal status, age, and personal nutrition³. Anagen - Active growth phase [6-8 years], Catagen - Transition -phase [1-2 weeks], Telogen - Resting phase [5-6 weeks], Exogen - Shedding phase. The overall chemical composition of hair is 45% carbon, 28% oxygen, 5% nitrogen, 7% hydrogen, and 5% sulphur⁴. The hair shaft is composed of keratin. Hair keratin is hard, compact, and strong. This fibrous protein is gradually formed inside cells from the germinal layer⁵. The main aim of the study is to design and evaluation of versatile Herbal Hair Oil to prevent and control hair-related problems⁶. The main objectives of the study are Provides hair conditioning, Prevention & control of hair fall, Reduce scalp irritation, Prevents premature greying of hair, Treats Dandruff, Relieves all types of headaches especially migraine & Hangover headaches gives a shiny and glossy appearance⁷.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of Herbal Hair Oil

Collection of all herbs from the medicinal garden Drying of leaves for at least 3-4 days by shade drying technique, the dried leaves were powdered by hand crushing. Powders were weighed accurately according to the formulae⁸. The weighed powders were mixed into the oil and macerated for 7 days along with heating for 10 min per a day. First Filtration was carried out by using muslin cloth and filtrate (oil) was collected⁹. To the above marc fresh oil is added again and it was allowed for maceration for 7 days along with heating for 10min per a day. The second filtration was carried out and oil was collected. The oil which was collected were filled into bottles and labeled. Samples were given to the consumers for evaluate the activity and then collected the feedback from consumers¹⁰.

Evaluation of Multi-Purpose Herbal Hair Oil

pH of the herbal oil was detected by using a pH meter, Viscosity was determined by using Ostwald's viscometer. Color, Odour, and State were determined manually¹¹. The oil was applied on hand and exposed to sunlight for 5 minutes to check for any irritation over the skin

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. For which age group this oil is suitable?
103 responses

2. Is this oil effective in controlling dandruff?
103 responses

3. Is this oil safe for hair?
103 responses

4. How often should I use it to see results?
103 responses

5. Does this oil blacken the hair?
103 responses

6. Is this oil effective in treating headache?
103 responses

7. Is this hair oil effective in reducing scalp irritations?
103 responses

8. Does this hair have any smoothy appearance after applying this oil?
103 responses

9. Is this oil effective in preventing premature gray hair?
103 responses

10. Is this oil causing any stickiness after application?
103 responses

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11. Does this hair oil shows any side effects?

103 responses

12. Did you observe hair regrowth after using this oil?

102 responses

13. Does this hair oil reduces split ends?

103 responses

14. Does this hair oil give conditioning to your hair?

102 responses

Evaluation of multi-purpose herbal hair oil

S. No	Parameters	Observations
1	Colour	Greenish Brown
2	Odour	Characteristic
3	State	Liquid
4	pH	6.3
5	Viscosity	0.8120 poise
6	Irritation	No Irritation

Herbal hair oil is the most well-recognized hair treatment. It helps to treat dry scalp and dry hair and it promotes natural hair growth. It also helps to treat dandruff. This multi-purpose herbal hair oil is very useful to reduce migraine headaches and mainly it reduces hangover headaches. In fig (1) we observed that 77% of people had given a response that this hair oil is suitable for all age groups. In fig (2) we observed that 95% of people had given a positive response in controlling dandruff. In fig (3) we observed that 98% of people had given a positive response that this hair oil is safe. In fig (4) we observed that 72% of responses offered to use this oil daily. In fig (5) we observed that 65% of people had given positive response that this oil blackens the hair. In fig (6) we observed that 91% of responses shows that this oil is effective in treating headache. In fig (7) we observed that 95% of people submitted that this oil is reducing scalp irritations. In fig (8) we observed that 82% of people observed smooth appearance after applying this herbal hair oil. In fig (9) we observed that 66% of people seen the activity of preventing premature grey hair. In fig (10) we observed that 94% of people seen no stickiness after applying the hair oil. In fig (11) we observed that there are no side effects after using this hair oil. In fig (12) we observed that 88% of hair regrowth is observed after using this herbal hair oil. In fig (13) we observed that 86% of people given a positive response in reducing hair split ends.

In fig (14) we observed that 89% of people had given a positive response about conditioning to hair.

CONCLUSION

Overall, this formulation provides us much nourishing value to our hair. The final/finished product is within the limits and since all the ingredients are natural and have many benefits, they are very useful to our hair. And finally, this herbal hair oil does not cause any damage to the hair.

LIMITATIONS

The responses are yet to be collected from larger population. Still the research is going on how the herbal hair oil is effective in treating the migraine and hangover headache.

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